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TYPES AND FORMS OF USE OF IMPERATIVE SENTENCES IN AZERBAIJAN LANGUAGE

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Abstract

The article mainly elaborates imperative sentence, which is one of the types of simple sentence. It is noted that imperative sentences in the Azerbaijani language express the speaker's insistence, suggestion, request, advice, will, invitation to perform a certain work. The meanings expressed in imperative sentences are determined by intonation, and sometimes by the meaning of verbs. Attention is paid to command sentences expressed by verbs and command words, which are types of imperative sentences. The article also points out that imperative sentences have different meanings and nuances of processing. At the same time, it is shown that adverbs are used to create certain subtleties of meaning in imperative sentences.

Keywords: imperative sentence, advice, request, prohibition, wish, admonition, politeness, intonation, particle, type.

According to the purpose of expression and intonation in the Azerbaijani language, one of the types of the sentence is the imperative sentence. Adil Babayev divides simple sentences according to purpose and intonation into the following groups: declarative, interrogative, exclamation and imperative. Imperative sentence means command, request, advice. For example:

Durma yıxıl yat hələ, Fərhad kişi,

Əsri görüb qalma belə mat, kişi! (Sabir) [1,p.132]

Imperative sentences express the speaker's insistence, suggestion, request, advice, admonition, invitation to perform a certain task. The meanings expressed in imperative sentences are determined by intonation, and sometimes by the meaning of verbs.

Imperative sentences expressing insistence are usually pronounced with a high intonation, advice, reminder, admonition while imperative sentences expressing request are pronounced with a relatively low intonation.

With the imperative form of the verb, two subjects are usually indicated, the first is the person who speaks, by whom the work is requested to be done, and the second is the person who performs the work.

The subject - the one who commands is not expressed grammatically, and the person to whom the case is directed finds its expression in separate words (eg: Come to us).

According to the expression of the news, there are two types of imperative sentences: 1. Imperative sentences with verbal predicates

2. Imperative sentences expressed by command words

In most cases, the predicate of imperative sentences is expressed by imperative verbs.

The subject is omitted in imperative sentences. In this respect, they are similar to simple sentences. Therefore, it is no coincidence that some linguists, for example, K. A. Meiselman, show that imperative sentences form a bridge between incomplete and single-component sentences. Unlike incomplete sentences, imperative sentences have semantic integrity and can be processed outside the text and are grammatically well-

formed. Different shades of meaning are reflected in imperative sentences.

Imperative sentences whose predicate is expressed in the first person singular and plural do not express insistence because the first person cannot command by himself. Thus, the command is given by the first person to another. In imperative sentences whose predicate is expressed in the first person singular, the desire and willing of the speaker to do a certain work is stated: For example: *Mən zəng eliyim görüm, bu Gülşən harda qaldı* (M. Süleymanov), *Yaxşı, gedim, yoxsa qarı məni boşayar, - deyə qoca usta çox çətin sezilən bir tərzdə gülümsədi* (H.Mehdi).

The following meanings are reflected in imperative sentences whose predicate is expressed in the first person plural:

a) Invitation is expressed; for example: *Ölkəyə daha çox pambıq verək. Camışçılıq təsərrüfatının yüksəlməsinə nail olaq.*

b) Request or offer is expressed; for example: *Gəl gedək nar dərəcəyə, Nar budağın əyməyə, Al yaşıla bürünüb qardaşa qız görməyə* (Bayatılar) ; *Oturub bi raz danışaq görək nə var, nə yox. Xahiş edirəm, mümkünsə o qızı evlərinə apararaq.*

Imperative sentences whose predicate is expressed in the second person singular and plural have the following meanings.

1. Insistence or demand is expressed. The most common type of statement of incitement is a command, which is a definite request to do something. Such sentences are usually short; For example: *Mən səndən tələb edirəm söylə uşaq kimindir; Sus ay külək, Sus ey tufan ! Sən səsinə kəs!* In such sentences, the word expressed with personal pronouns is usually omitted. A.M. Peshkovsky showed its reason very right: „ *The omission of personal pronouns is a grammatical sign of definite imperative. On the contrary, the use of this pronoun weakens the command and gives it the tone of a request*”.

In imperative sentences, particles are used to create certain nuances of meaning; e.g: *Gəl inad göstərmə eşqinə qarşı...*(S.Vurgun) ; *Salam söyləyək, gəl əsən*

yellərə, Aparsın qoy onu uzaq ellərə ... (S.Rustam). These particles do not have any serious role in the formation of imperative sentences. Imperative sentences are formed and processed independently of them. However, these particles express certain relationships in imperative sentences, strengthen the meaning in imperative sentences, make them insisting. That's why the imperative sentences used with the particle are different from the imperative sentences without the particle. Taking this into account, in the linguistics references, sometimes these sentences are divided into two parts: particled and non-particled imperative sentences [2. p. 126-127].

Insistence is much stronger when the predicate of imperative sentence is in the second person singular with the particle -sana (sənə), and in the second person plural with the particle -sınız (səniz). The use of such suffixed predicate is more characteristic of colloquial language; e.g: *Uşaq məsələsini danışsana; Əl çəksənə nə vermisən ala bilmirsən.*

2. Advises, admonition, reassures. In the advice, there is an incitement to any work, but its importance is not expressed. Through advice, the idea can be expressed more forcefully; e.g: *Darixma oğlun, allah qoysa, bir neçə günə sağalıb duracaqsan və səni gəzməyə aparacağam* (S.S.Akhundov); *Öyrənin, balalarım, bilin ki, o yoldaşlar sizin xoşxətliyinizdən ötrü qurban gediblər* (H. Mehdi).

Advice and admonition in imperative sentences, whose predicate is expressed in the second person singular, often refer to the general person as well. This general figure includes the interlocutor of the speaker. We find this type of imperative sentences mostly in proverbs [5]; e.g: *Əvvəl arxı tulan, sonra bərəkəllah de* (Atalar sözü); *Yüz ölçç bir biç* (Atalar sözü).

3. It express anger; e.g: *Rədd ol qapıdan, ağılama zar-zar, dilənçi. Bu saat rədd ol xarabana, çix, çix, eşidirsənmi?* (J. Jabbarly).

4. It expresses request, suggestion, begging, wish. The request is used when the speaker is unable to force the implementation of his wish, or cannot provoke due to embarrassment. Nevertheless, activity and intensity have a stronger effect on work performance. The request is pronounced somewhat slowly and extended; e.g: *Gəl, gəl ay yaz günləri ilin əziz günləri* (M. A. Sabir).

5. It expresses applause, gratitude; e.g: *Sağ ol vətən oğlu, Sağ ol qardaşım.*

6. It expresses invitation, demand; e.g: *Sülh uğrunda mübarizədə xalqların birliyini möhkəmləndirin.*

Imperative sentences whose predicate is expressed in the singular or plural of the third person express the following meanings:

1. It expresses insistence; e.g: *Bu saat bu kəddən çıxsın. Dustağ edilsinlər. Uzun sözün qıyası, onlar qulluğa qaytarılsınlar.*

2. It expresses applause; e.g: *Var olsun azad yurdun azad oğulları.*

3. It expresses anger; e.g: *Yerə girsin. Yox olsun. Onu görüm, yerə batsın.*

Particles are often used in the sentences whose predicate is expressed by the command form of the verb

which reinforce the meanings such as insistence, invitation, advice, sarcasm, desire, etc. In the sentences expressed by the imperative form of the verb, there are also words and phrases that serve to express the meaning of the emirate in a stronger way [3].

In imperative sentences expressing request, beginning, mostly words and expressions such as *zəhmət olmasa, sən allah, mən ölüm, aman günüdür, amandır, aman, sən olasan öz allahın, başına dolanım* are used, which make the request, the plea even stronger.

Imperative sentences expressing insistence contain the following words and phrases; *vəssalam, de* classification forms of the verb *feilin təsri formaları* (for example: *deyirəm, dedilər*), *nə cür olursa olsun və s.*, e.g: *Gərək düzəlsin, vəssalam. Vur dedim, vur. Sənə deyirəm, götür onları buradan.*

In sentences where the predicate is expressed by the imperative form of the verb, the predicate is often repeated in order to express the insistence and request more prominently [4]. One of the means that strengthens the motivation is repetition [7]. In imperative sentences, the word expressing the main content of the stimulus is repeated twice or more. The repeated word is active, forceful and usually expressed in a high tone. Repetition occurs in both verb and non-verb sentences; e.g: *Qurtar məni burdan, Aqşın qurtar. Get, get. Oynasınlar, oynasınlar.*

When the speaker wants to convey his opinion to the interlocutor not by insistence, but in the form of advice, desire, before the imperative sentence, he uses a simple sentence expressed by one of the verbs to say, to want, to wish, in the first person singular or plural of this or that tense of the predicate form; e.g: *Mən deyirəm ki, vətəndaş kimi o öz nöqsanlarını bilir.*

a) Imperative sentences whose predicate is expressed by the imperative form of the verb

Such sentences indicate that the performance of work, situation or action is important. It belongs to all three persons singular or plural; e.g: *Mən firtınalı günlərdə də təhlükədən çəkinməməliyəm. Qanun qarşısında bütün bəşəriyyət bərabər olmalıdır. Sən bu gün getməlisən.*

Imperative sentences that are imperative and do not accept any person suffix are invitational. In such sentences, work, situation or action refers to a certain group of people; e.g: *Yazıcılar qurultayının yekunlarını öyrənməli və təbliğ etməli.*

Due to the stylistic features of verb tenses and suffixes, imperative sentences can be expressed with other forms of the verb.

b) Imperative sentences whose predicate is expressed by the subjunctive mood

The sentence in imperative sentences, whose predicate is expressed by subjunctive mood, is sometimes pronounced in a high tone. At this time, the speaker asks or demands his interlocutor to do this or that work; e.g: *Xahiş edirəm bu saat durub donumu gətirəsan.*

c) Imperative sentences whose predicate is expressed by indicative mood

In imperative sentences whose predicate is in the second person or plural of the indefinite future, the execution of work, situation or action can be expressed in

the form of insistence; e.g: *Materiallar hazır olan kimi yola düşərsən.*

d) Infinitive-Imperative sentences

I. Infinitives - command sentences find their expression in sentences whose execution is final and important. Infinitive - sentence in imperative sentences often refers to concrete, and sometimes to indefinite time; e.g: *Lap ciyərini çəkib sinəsindən çıxarmaq.*

II. Imperative sentences expressed by command words

There is a group of words that are used only in the third person singular and form imperative sentences. In such sentences, the final judgment is expressed; e.g: *Genə başladın? Ağlamaq nədir uşaqsan Bəsdir, bəsdir. Kifayətdir, Yusif, başım fırlanır. Məni qocaltdınız, daha bəsdir, məni çərlətdiniz, daha bəsdir.* [6, p. 152-157]

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